

ANALYSIS OF NETWORK PACKETS USING WIRESHARK SOFTWARE TO DETECT IOT NETWORK VULNERABILITIES

"IOT QURILMALARIDA KIBERXAVFSIZLIKNING ZAIFLIKLARINI ANIQLASH: ALGORITMLAR VA MODELLAR"

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Annotation

This research describes the process of analyzing network packets using the Wireshark program to detect vulnerabilities in IoT networks[1]. The interconnectedness of IoT devices demands security, and identifying anomalous activity between these devices is crucial. The research tests algorithms to detect anomalies in IoT devices.

Keywords: *IoT Network Vulnerabilities, Wireshark Analysis, Network Packet Analysis, IoT Security, Anomaly Detection, Cybersecurity, Protocol Analysis (TCP, UDP, HTTP, MQTT)*

Introduction

As IoT networks expand, ensuring their security and reliability becomes increasingly important. Security vulnerabilities in IoT devices can lead to various threats in network traffic. Analyzing IoT network traffic to identify vulnerabilities is thus a significant concern.

Wireshark is a widely used tool for analyzing network packets and is effective for examining packets transmitted in IoT networks[2]. It aids in detecting vulnerabilities within the network. In network security and analysis, collecting and analyzing network packets is critical. Wireshark is a common open-source tool for recording and analyzing network traffic. This article discusses packet capturing, applying filters, and analysis methods with Wireshark.

For analyzing network packets and detecting vulnerabilities in IoT networks using Wireshark, several important aspects should be considered. Wireshark is a powerful tool that allows for the real-time capture and analysis of network traffic, which is essential for identifying potential security issues[3].

Wireshark enables users to capture detailed data packets from network communication, including protocol information, packet payloads, and other metadata. It supports a wide range of network protocols, including TCP, UDP, and

ICMP, and allows you to filter and analyze traffic specific to IoT devices. For instance, you can use filters like `ip.dst == your_device_ip && tcp` to narrow down traffic to packets directed at specific devices

Additionally, Wireshark is particularly useful for detecting network anomalies and potential security threats such as unauthorized access attempts, DoS attacks, or the use of unencrypted data[4]. However, it's important to understand that Wireshark is not an intrusion detection system (IDS) and doesn't offer automated alerts for suspicious activity. Instead, it helps users identify abnormal traffic patterns and malformed packets that may indicate a security vulnerability.

For effective use in IoT network security, it is also critical to understand the network protocols and the communication patterns of IoT devices. By analyzing the data packets captured from the network, you can gain valuable insights into the behaviors of IoT devices and spot vulnerabilities like unencrypted communication or weak authentication mechanisms

Methods

Wireshark (formerly known as Ethereal) is a FOSS (Free and Open-Source Software) network protocol analyzer. It can be used for troubleshooting network issues and analyzing protocols like TCP, DNS, and HTTP. Wireshark has many features that distinguish it from similar tools:

- Real-time packet capturing and offline analysis.
- Packet details in a human-readable format.
- Packet color-coding rules.

Capturing Packets with Wireshark

Wireshark allows capturing network traffic to analyze specific activities or network attacks. During packet collection, various network protocols, IP addresses, ports, and other parameters can be filtered to highlight important details. In IoT networks, Wireshark can analyze packets to detect any anomalies. Using Wireshark, the following processes can be executed:

• **Selecting Network Interface and Data Collection:** Wireshark enables selecting a network interface to capture packets between IoT devices.

• **Filtering:** Through protocol-based filters, such as MQTT, HTTP, and UDP, important packets are identified and analyzed.

• **Detecting Anomalous Activity:** By checking packet numbers, ports, and IP addresses, network changes and unusual activities are identified.

Applying Wireshark Filters:

Wireshark filters can be used for quick packet analysis. Filters allow displaying only necessary packets and analyzing network traffic for a specific purpose. For example:

1. Filtering IP addresses (`ip.addr == 192.168.1.1`).
2. Protocol-based filtering (e.g., HTTP, FTP, TCP).
3. Filtering by packet size or time.
4. This article uses Kali Linux as the operating system.

Results

Using Wireshark, network protocols such as TCP, UDP, and DNS were analyzed. This analysis identified packet details, including IP addresses, ports, protocols, and potential security vulnerabilities. By applying filters, Wireshark effectively highlighted specific network characteristics in the captured packets. Once Wireshark was launched, a list of available devices for packet capture was displayed.

The screenshot shows the packet list pane in Wireshark, displaying five captured packets. The columns are 'No.', 'Time', 'Source', 'Destination', 'Protocol', and 'Length Info'.

No.	Time	Source	Destination	Protocol	Length Info
1	0.000000000	2409:4043:2001:4a5:...	ff02::fb	MDNS	102 Standard query 0x0000 PTR
2	0.000000032	192.168.18.150	224.0.0.251	MDNS	82 Standard query 0x0000 PTR
3	6.978017638	42:38:fb:8b:60:9f	Broadcast	ARP	60 Who has 192.168.18.150? Tel
4	23.830689783	0.0.0.0	255.255.255.255	DHCP	336 DHCP Request - Transaction
5	37.697548600	42:38:fb:8b:60:9f	Broadcast	ARP	60 Who has 192.168.18.150? Tel

Wireshark Color Coding: Wireshark uses different color schemes to distinguish traffic types. For example, light blue for UDP, purple for TCP, and black for packets with errors. To view and modify the meaning of these colors, go to *View > Coloring Rules*.

Filtering Packets with Wireshark: To filter in Wireshark, use the search bar at the top of the packet list or the summary table. To filter TCP traffic, enter "TCP" in the search bar. Wireshark also includes primary filters under *Analyze > Display Filters*.

Inspecting Packets with Wireshark: To view various details, click on a packet in the summary table that describes the traffic. This also provides another way to create custom filters.

Wireshark Test Driver: Here, we provide a practical example of capturing and inspecting traffic on a network interface using Wireshark. In our setup, we installed Wireshark on Kali Linux and can interact with the "eth0" wired interface.

Searching for TCP Protocol Packets: We look for TCP packets and use the filter panel to filter these connections. Many background processes on the system accessing the network exchange packets with external networks. Using Wireshark's filtering function, we filter packets directed to our system. For example, to filter TCP packets destined for our system, use the filter: ip.dst == your_system_ip && tcp.

Discussion

Wireshark is highly significant in identifying network security vulnerabilities. It allows for the detection of network changes, protocol analysis, and the identification of weak points. By providing real-time network traffic monitoring, Wireshark plays an essential role in enhancing security.

Conclusion

Wireshark is an effective tool for identifying and analyzing vulnerabilities in IoT networks, playing a crucial role in strengthening network security. It is indispensable for network monitoring and security assurance.

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